

FORMS OF ORGANIC CARBON IN SOILS FROM ETSAKO EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF EDO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study focuses on the forms and distribution of organic carbon content in the soils of Etsako East Local Government Area. The soil samples were physically fractionated into labile organic carbon and recalcitrant organic carbon following standard methods in the laboratory to understand soil organic carbon dynamics and the effect on land use and selected physical-chemical properties of the soils were also determined. In all it was observed that the labile organic carbon accounted for 13 percent of the total organic carbon while the recalcitrant organic carbon accounts for 87 percent indicating that the recalcitrant organic carbon is of a greater proportion than the labile organic carbon. These fractions of organic carbon were also decreasing with depth. The soil organic carbon is low. The study revealed the different land uses contributed to the relatively low level of labile organic carbon in the soil hence appropriate crop and soil management practices are required in maintaining or improving the organic carbon status of the soil.

Key words: forms, distribution, labile organic carbon, recalcitrant organic carbon

1. Introduction

Studies have shown that soil hosts the largest terrestrial carbon pool (Scharlemann, *et al.*, 2014) which plays a crucial role in the global carbon balance by regulating dynamic biogeochemical processes and the exchange of greenhouse gases (GHG) with the atmosphere (Lal, 2013) and it has also been estimated that about one third of Carbon of plant residues is retained in soil organic matter (SOM) (Tank, 2003). Soil organic matter (SOM) is the most important indicators of soil quality, which is the building block for the soil structure, formation of stable aggregates, and is able to improve the infiltration rates and, the storage capacity for water (Jones, *et al.* 2005). SOM is used to describe organic constituents such as tissues from dead plants and animals, materials less than 2mm in size, and soil organisms. The formation of soil organic

matter (SOM) is a very complex process (Haynes, 2005); it makes up only 5% to 10% of the volume of soil (less than 5% of the weight) but it is critical in holding soil particles together, storing nutrient and feeding soil organisms. Soil organic matter is the carbon source of many organisms and it is a build-up in the decayed plant and animal residues (Kogel-Knabner, 2002; Marteus, *et al.*, 2003). SOM can be divided into different pools based on the time needed for full decomposition and the derived residence time of the products in the soil (turnover time) as Fast pool (labile or active pool), Intermediate pool (mineral associated organic carbon) and Slow pool (recalcitrant or stable pool) (FAO and ITPS, 2015; O'Rourke *et al.*, 2015; Gougoulis *et al.*, 2014). According to literature there are different techniques that partition the fractions into functional pool but physical fractionation process is able to

disintegrate the soil organic carbon (SOC) particles in order to effectively detect the labile organic carbon fraction as opposed to the chemical method which may provide underestimated values of the fractions because of surface attack (Baldock, *et al.*2000); Hence, the use of sieves to separate SOC fractions was employed following the study by Christensen, 2001 were labile fractions are found between sieves of sizes 53–250 μm and the recalcitrant ones $< 53 \mu\text{m}$. This technique has allowed much information to be gained on the location and dynamics of SOM and the effects on land use.

2. Materials and Methods

Study Area: The site location is based on the soil formation characteristics which are geology, vegetation, topography, time and rainfall; and they all affect the parent materials, hence, the location is Etsako East Local Government area which is the derived Savanna area of Edo State. The sampling was done randomly at depths of 0-15cm (topsoil) and 15-30cm (subsoil) at 20 different points. The location has an area of 1,133 km^2 with coordinates 7.10649N, 6.69027E.

Table 1: Description of the sampling points at the location

S/N	Sampled Point	Depth (cm)	Northing (N)	Easting (E)	Land Use	Town/Villages
1	SP1a	0-15	7.142616293	6.705203629	Forest land	Unuedegor (W/side)
2	SP1b	15-30				
3	SP2a	0-15	7.106779372	6.700151763	Flood Land	Bode (W/side)
4	SP2b	15-30				
5	SP3a	0-15	7.065013827	6.596818148	Arable Land	Ekwosto Weppa
6	SP3b	15-30				
7	SP4a	0-15	7.055428093	6.576575182	Cashew Plantation	Agiere Weppa
8	SP4b	15-30				
9	SP5a	0-15	7.049033613	6.554887178	Grass Land	Aviodor Weppa
10	SP5b	15-30				
11	SP6a	0-15	7.030114455	6.528526055	Cashew Plantation land	Iviari Weppa
12	SP6b	15-30				
13	SP7a	0-15	7.070024078	6.616768981	Cashew Plantation land	Isaeh Shrine Weppa
14	SP7b	15-30				
15	SP8a	0-15	7.07943391	6.656087699	Arable Land	Emekweme-Bode
16	SP8b	15-30				
17	SP9a	0-15	7.106593124	6.682724924	Shrubs land	Upland Bode
18	SP9b	15-30				
19	SP10a	0-15	7.11897845	6.64914616	Build-up Area	Ivioghe Bode
20	SP10b	15-30				
21	SP11a	0-15	7.118943854	6.635265757	Secondary Forest	Edegbe Bode
22	SP11b	15-30				
23	SP12a	0-15	7.09508939	6.558064779	Secondary Forest	Othamhe Bode
24	SP12b	15-30				
25	SP13a	0-15	7.104246747	6.592995638	Secondary Forest	Iviukwe Bode
26	SP13b	15-30				
27	SP14a	0-15	7.121559105	6.613011009	Arable Land	Onkholhe Bode
28	SP14b	15-30				
29	SP15a	0-15	7.139152634	6.504672956	Forest	Iviukwa Bode
30	SP15b	15-30				
31	SP16a	0-15	7.125519773	6.620392254	Grass Land	Iviebua Bode
32	SP16b	15-30				
33	SP17a	0-15	7.130402697	6.641975515	Cashew Plantation land	Eigode Village
34	SP17b	15-30				
35	SP18a	0-15	7.153953853	6.650225423	Arable Land	Itogbo Bode
36	SP18b	15-30				
37	SP19a	0-15	7.166855337	6.636820285	Cassava Farm land	Uzany Community
38	SP19b	15-30				
39	SP20a	0-15	7.137353817	6.666978668	Grass Land	Egor Village
40	SP20b	15-30				

SP-Sampling Point

Figure 1: Map of Etsako East Local Government Area showing the sampling locations.

The soil samples were subjected to laboratory analyses after they have been air dried and sieved with 2 mm sieve for the determination of Particulate SOM fraction (Labile fraction) and Recalcitrant SOM fraction (stable fraction) via physical fractionation method by Christensen, 2001. 20 g of air dried sub-sample was weighed into 250 ml plastic bottle and 105 ml of distilled water added, the mixture was shaken for 1 hour on an end to end shaker. The content was passed through 53 μm sieve. The sample above the 53 μm and the sample that passed through the sieve was considered as the Particulate (Labile fraction) and Recalcitrant (Stable fraction) respectively, they were collected and oven dried at 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ so as not to destroy the Carbon contained in the samples. The oven dried samples were reduced into powder form using mortar and pestle and then analyzed for organic carbon content using Modified Walkley and Black wet-oxidation method (Anand, *et al.* 2022). 5 g of soil sample was weighed and transferred to a dried 500 ml conical flask. Add 10 ml of 1N $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ and 20 ml of concentrated sulphuric

acid (H_2SO_4) added and mixed by gentle swirling. The flask was allowed to cool for the mixture to react hence, it was kept for about 30 minutes. After the reaction is over, the content was diluted with 200 ml of distilled water and then 10 ml o-phosphoric acid was added followed by 1 ml of diphenylamine indicator. The sample was then titrated with 0.4N Ferrous Ammonium Sulphate (FAS) till the colour changed to brilliant green at the end point. The process was repeated for blank with same quantity of the chemicals but without soil.

Calculation:

- a. % Carbon = $(1-T/S) (3.951/g)$
- b. % Organic Matter = % Carbon $\times 1.724$

Where,

g = wt. of sample in g

S = ml of FAS with blank titration

T = ml of FAS with sample titration

The factor 1.724 is based on the assumption that carbon is only 58 % of the organic matter (Pribyl, 2010).

The average oxidation number for organic carbon is assumed as zero and the reaction involved is as follows: -

And

Statistical analysis

The data collected was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Gensat method. A simple linear regression analysis was also being used to reveal the relationship between SOC and the physical-chemical properties.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 2: Result of selected physical and chemical properties of the soils for 0-15 cm and 15-30 cm depths.

S/N	pH	EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	OM (%)	OC (%)	Total N (%)	C:N	P (mg kg^{-1})	Ex. K (cmolkg^{-1})	Ex. Na (cmolkg^{-1})
1	3.9	408	2.03	1.18	0.658	1.79	4.45	0.32	0.01
2	3.7	121	0.22	0.45	0.461	0.98	1.94	0.31	0.05
3	3.9	778	12.10	7.02	0.471	14.90	53.98	0.67	1.23
4	4.6	236	19.53	11.33	0.438	25.87	55.81	0.70	0.97
5	5.8	364	2.29	1.79	0.128	13.98	17.40	0.33	0.42
6	6.2	126	0.60	0.35	1.029	0.34	0.33	0.42	7.24
7	3.7	365	1.28	0.74	0.576	1.28	3.25	0.32	0.73
8	4.6	79	0.55	0.32	0.370	0.86	4.65	0.31	0.89
9	4.8	348	1.55	1.31	1.259	1.04	3.68	0.33	0.83
10	4.5	169	0.52	0.30	0.712	0.42	2.34	0.32	1.75
11	5.1	207	0.83	0.93	0.667	1.39	1.45	0.30	0.74
12	6.2	79	0.60	0.35	0.518	0.68	0.63	0.30	0.71
13	5.5	149	0.78	0.45	0.395	1.14	6.61	0.30	0.70
14	5.7	36	0.45	0.26	0.716	0.36	4.99	0.29	0.82
15	5.3	262	0.10	0.74	1.881	0.39	1.97	0.30	0.55
16	5.8	96	0.33	0.19	0.724	0.26	4.02	0.30	0.77
17	5.9	226	0.22	0.61	0.255	2.39	1.45	0.30	0.71
18	6.2	84	0.28	0.16	0.173	0.92	0.54	0.15	0.66
19	5.8	221	0.22	0.80	0.136	5.88	1.11	0.30	0.74
20	6.2	69	0.17	0.35	0.104	3.37	0.67	0.29	0.69
21	4.5	326	1.33	0.77	0.089	8.65	2.28	0.29	0.63
22	6.3	70	0.66	0.38	0.119	3.19	1.11	0.24	0.15
23	4.8	413	2.53	1.47	0.107	14.55	2.42	0.34	0.80
24	5.6	162	0.81	1.06	0.260	4.08	1.08	0.29	0.65
25	5.8	288	1.90	1.10	0.125	8.84	1.15	0.31	0.67
26	6.1	91	0.88	0.71	0.130	5.46	0.60	0.22	0.47
27	5.5	167	0.93	0.54	0.157	3.44	3.05	0.29	0.65
28	5.0	71	0.78	0.45	0.092	4.89	0.91	0.19	0.67
29	4.0	372	1.83	1.06	0.089	11.91	2.85	0.29	0.67
30	4.1	178	0.85	0.50	0.096	5.48	2.13	0.29	0.72
31	5.3	171	1.33	0.77	0.130	5.92	1.23	0.29	0.66
32	5.9	95	0.72	0.42	0.109	3.85	0.77	0.33	0.77
33	5.0	138	0.88	0.51	0.091	5.60	1.23	0.30	0.65
34	4.3	71	0.83	0.48	0.126	3.81	0.83	0.18	0.28
35	5.1	210	1.79	1.04	0.213	5.79	3.88	0.30	0.69
36	5.1	73	0.88	0.51	0.173	2.95	1.00	0.29	0.72
37	5.6	232	0.22	1.09	0.136	8.02	9.03	0.30	0.68
38	5.7	79	1.16	0.67	0.198	3.38	7.07	0.30	0.67
39	4.8	164	1.43	0.83	0.133	6.24	4.40	0.29	0.67
40	4.8	62	0.75	0.44	0.149	3.44	3.07	0.25	0.64

EC=Electrical Conductivity, OM=Organic Matter, OC=Organic Carbon, Total N=Total Nitrogen, C:N=Carbon-Nitrogen Ratio, P=Phosphorus, Ex K=Exchangeable Potassium. Ex. Na=Exchangeable Sodium

Table 2: Result of selected physical and chemical properties of the soils for 0-15 cm and 15-30 cm depth, cont'd.

S/N	Ex. Ca (cmolkg ⁻¹)	Ex. Mg (cmolkg ⁻¹)	CEC (cmolkg ⁻¹)	Ex .H ⁺ (cmolkg ⁻¹)	Al ³⁺ (cmolkg ⁻¹)	ECEC (cmolkg ⁻¹)	Clay (%)	Silt (%)	Sand (%)
1	2.00	1.04	3.37	0.005	0.015	3.390	3.3	4.3	92.4
2	1.12	1.00	2.48	0.007	0.015	2.487	7.3	5.3	87.4
3	7.04	8.08	17.02	0.006	0.015	17.026	5.3	27.3	67.4
4	4.72	20.72	27.11	0.007	0.015	27.117	5.3	1.3	93.4
5	7.24	1.68	9.67	0.005	0.015	9.670	3.3	1.3	95.4
6	1.68	9.67	0.01	0.007	0.015	4.427	5.3	4.3	90.4
7	1.20	4.24	6.49	0.008	0.003	6.501	3.3	5.3	91.4
8	1.92	0.64	3.76	0.006	0.003	3.766	4.3	10.3	85.4
9	3.92	1.60	6.68	0.005	0.003	6.685	3.2	10.5	86.3
10	2.36	1.12	4.68	0.006	0.003	4.681	7.7	12.0	80.3
11	3.44	1.04	5.52	0.006	0.003	5.526	3.2	9.5	87.3
12	0.32	1.84	3.17	0.006	0.003	3.176	4.2	10.5	85.3
13	1.68	0.88	3.56	0.006	0.003	3.566	3.2	1.5	95.3
14	1.20	0.16	2.47	0.005	0.003	3.478	4.2	4.5	91.3
15	1.78	0.76	3.39	0.004	0.003	2.895	3.2	3.5	93.3
16	1.04	0.56	2.67	0.009	0.003	2.679	10.2	5.5	84.3
17	2.80	0.72	4.53	0.004	0.003	4.537	3.2	1.5	95.3
18	1.68	0.08	2.57	0.006	0.003	2.576	3.2	2.5	94.3
19	3.04	1.04	5.12	0.005	0.003	5.125	3.2	2.5	95.3
20	2.62	0.60	4.20	0.006	0.003	4.201	4.2	4.0	91.8
21	8.24	2.00	11.16	0.010	0.006	11.176	4.2	5.5	90.3
22	0.40	0.56	1.35	0.011	0.015	1.376	12.2	4.5	83.3
23	4.64	1.52	7.30	0.008	0.003	7.311	3.2	4.5	92.3
24	2.32	0.88	4.14	0.006	0.003	4.149	5.5	4.5	90.0
25	3.84	1.40	6.21	0.006	0.003	6.216	3.5	1.9	94.6
26	3.20	0.64	4.53	0.005	0.003	4.535	4.5	2.4	95.1
27	1.36	0.96	2.66	0.004	0.003	2.664	3.5	2.4	94.1
28	0.96	0.08	1.90	0.007	0.006	1.913	5.5	1.4	93.1
29	0.32	1.20	2.48	0.004	0.006	2.484	3.3	1.4	95.1
30	0.68	0.68	2.37	0.006	0.006	2.371	4.0	0.9	95.1
31	2.88	0.40	4.23	0.004	0.006	4.234	3.5	1.4	95.1
32	2.40	0.08	3.58	0.003	0.003	3.586	3.5	3.4	93.1
33	0.72	0.96	2.61	0.006	0.003	2.616	3.5	2.4	94.1
34	0.32	1.12	1.79	0.005	0.015	1.810	6.5	2.4	91.1
35	2.84	2.52	6.35	0.005	0.015	6.350	3.5	2.4	94.1
36	1.04	0.32	2.37	0.002	0.009	2.381	4.5	2.4	93.1
37	4.08	0.96	5.07	0.002	0.006	5.078	3.5	1.4	95.1
38	2.64	0.56	4.17	0.004	0.006	4.174	4.5	2.4	93.1
39	0.96	0.64	2.56	0.005	0.003	2.568	4.5	1.1	94.4
40	0.64	0.48	2.01	0.005	0.005	2.019	5.5	2.1	92.4

Ex. Ca=Exchangeable Calcium, Ex Mg=Exchangeable Magnesium, CEC=Cation Exchange Capacity, Ex. H⁺=Exchangeable Hydrogen ion, Al³⁺= Aluminum ion, ECEC=Effective Cation Exchange Capacity.

Table 3: Result of TOC and its forms of the soils for 0-15 cm and 15-30 cm.

S/N	TOC(%)	LOC(%)	MAOC(%)	ROC(%)	%LOC%	%ROC%
1	1.18	0.63	0.55	4.98	11.00	89.00
2	0.45	0.36	0.09	1.98	15.00	85.00

3	7.02	6.67	0.35	4.59	59.00	41.00
4	11.33	10.03	1.30	5.97	63.00	37.00
5	1.79	1.65	0.14	5.20	24.00	76.00
6	0.35	0.20	0.15	1.90	10.00	90.00
7	0.74	0.48	0.26	2.50	16.00	84.00
8	0.32	0.22	0.10	1.67	12.00	88.00
9	1.31	0.91	0.40	3.05	23.00	77.00
10	0.30	0.22	0.08	1.36	14.00	86.00
11	0.93	0.53	0.40	3.16	14.00	86.00
12	0.35	0.21	0.14	0.65	24.00	76.00
13	0.45	0.15	0.30	4.44	3.00	97.00
14	0.26	0.05	0.21	1.93	3.00	97.00
15	0.74	0.49	0.25	2.48	16.00	84.00
16	0.19	0.15	0.04	1.03	13.00	87.00
17	0.61	0.38	0.23	5.76	6.00	94.00
18	0.16	0.04	0.12	2.56	2.00	98.00
19	0.80	0.39	0.41	5.27	7.00	93.00
20	0.35	0.11	0.24	2.26	5.00	95.00
21	0.77	0.36	0.41	3.99	8.00	92.00
22	0.38	0.20	0.18	1.38	13.00	87.00
23	1.47	1.24	0.23	5.27	19.00	81.00
24	1.06	0.90	0.16	2.67	25.00	75.00
25	1.10	0.62	0.48	7.34	8.00	92.00
26	0.51	0.16	0.35	2.35	6.00	94.00
27	0.54	0.24	0.30	6.15	4.00	96.00
28	0.45	0.20	0.25	2.91	6.00	94.00
29	1.06	0.66	0.40	6.61	9.00	91.00
30	0.50	0.17	0.33	1.95	8.00	92.00
31	0.77	0.36	0.41	5.12	7.00	93.00
32	0.42	0.10	0.32	2.04	4.00	95.00
33	0.51	0.21	0.30	4.03	5.00	95.00
34	0.48	0.06	0.42	1.36	4.00	96.00
35	1.04	0.53	0.51	4.10	11.00	89.00
36	0.58	0.32	0.26	2.15	13.00	87.00
37	1.09	0.23	0.86	3.88	6.00	94.00
38	0.67	0.42	0.25	2.26	16.00	84.00
39	0.83	0.52	0.31	4.93	10.00	90.00
40	0.44	0.20	0.24	1.89	10.00	90.00

TOC=Total Organic Carbon, LOC=Labile Organic Carbon, ROC=Recalcitrant Organic Carbon, MAOC=Mineral Associated Organic Carbon.
 %LOC=Percentage Labile Organic Carbon, %ROC=Recalcitrant Organic Carbon.

Table 4a: Co Efficient of Correlation of forms of Organic

S/N	Parameters	Sampled Depth (cm)	TOC %	LOC %	MAOC %	ROC %
1	pH	0-15	-0.375	-0.371	-0.011	0.265
2	EC(μ S/cm)	0-15	0.867	0.867	-0.062	0.003
3	Org. M(%)	0-15	0.977	0.978	-0.078	0.082
4	Org. C(%)	0-15	1.000	0.994	-0.021	0.019
5	Total N(%)	0-15	0.041	0.053	-0.124	-0.631
6	C:Nratio	0-15	0.547	0.548	-0.035	0.464
7	Av. P (mgkg ⁻¹)	0-15	0.963	0.960	-0.045	-0.015
8	CEC(cmolk ⁻¹)	0-15	0.808	0.809	-0.075	-0.116
9	Ex .K(cmolk ⁻¹)	0-15	0.983	0.991	-0.147	-0.021
10	Ex. Na(cmolk ⁻¹)	0-15	0.549	0.556	-0.115	-0.088
11	Ex.Ca(cmolk ⁻¹)	0-15	0.512	0.505	0.022	-0.029
12	Ex. Mg(cmolk ⁻¹)	0-15	0.867	0.869	-0.080	-0.182
13	Ex. H ⁺ (cmolk ⁻¹)	0-15	0.078	0.115	-0.354	-0.187
14	Ex.Al ³⁺ (cmolk ⁻¹)	0-15	-0.112	-0.151	0.379	0.017
15	ECEC (cmolk ⁻¹)	0-15	0.806	0.806	-0.068	-0.103
16	Clay(%)	0-15	0.725	0.718	0.025	0.047
17	Silt(%)	0-15	0.892	0.886	-0.036	-0.260
18	Sand(%)	0-15	-0.903	-0.897	0.032	0.241

EC=Electrical Conductivity, OM=Organic Matter, OC=Organic Carbon, Total N=Total Nitrogen, C: N=Carbon-Nitrogen Ratio, Av. P=Phosphorus, Ex K=Exchangeable Potassium. Ex. Na=Exchangeable Sodium, Ex. Ca=Exchangeable Calcium, Ex Mg=Exchangeable Magnesium, CEC=Cation Exchange Capacity, Ex. H⁺=Exchangeable Hydrogen ion, Al³⁺=Aluminum ion, ECEC=Effective Cation Exchange Capacity. Correlation coefficient= r, p <0.05: r<0.005 not significant>0.007 highly significant

Table 4b: Co Efficient of Correlation of forms of Organic

S/N	Parameters	Sampled Depth (cm)	TOC (%)	LOC (%)	MAOC (%)	ROC (%)
1	pH	15-30	-0.218	-0.216	-0.222	-0.222
2	EC(μ S/cm)	15-30	0.660	0.668	0.538	0.538
3	Org. M(%)	15-30	0.998	0.996	0.939	0.939
4	Org. C(%)	15-30	0.999	0.998	0.936	0.936
5	Total N(%)	15-30	0.060	0.085	-0.154	-0.154
6	C:Nratio	15-30	0.957	0.946	0.973	0.973
7	Av. P (mgkg ⁻¹)	15-30	0.985	0.986	0.903	0.903
8	CEC(cmolk ⁻¹)	15-30	0.978	0.978	0.902	0.902
9	Ex .K(cmolk ⁻¹)	15-30	0.844	0.852	0.713	0.713
10	Ex. Na(cmolk ⁻¹)	15-30	-0.018	-0.011	-0.080	-0.080
11	Ex.Ca(cmolk ⁻¹)	15-30	0.650	0.651	0.594	0.594

12	Ex. Mg(cmolkg ⁻¹)	15-30	0.900	0.902	0.811	0.811
13	Ex. H ⁺ (cmolkg ⁻¹)	15-30	0.105	0.125	-0.067	-0.067
14	Ex. Al ³⁺ (cmolkg ⁻¹)	15-30	-0.129	-0.147	0.029	0.029
15	ECEC (cmolkg ⁻¹)	15-30	0.982	0.983	0.898	0.898
16	Clay(%)	15-30	-0.041	-0.027	-0.163	-0.163
17	Silt(%)	15-30	-0.247	-0.221	-0.450	-0.450
18	Sand(%)	15-30	0.198	0.169	0.422	0.422

EC=Electrical Conductivity, OM=Organic Matter, OC=Organic Carbon, Total N=Total Nitrogen, C: N=Carbon-Nitrogen Ratio, Av. P=Phosphorus, Ex K=Exchangeable Potassium. Ex. Na=Exchangeable Sodium, Ex. Ca=Exchangeable Calcium, Ex Mg=Exchangeable Magnesium, CEC=Cation Exchange Capacity, Ex. H⁺=Exchangeable Hydrogen ion, Al³⁺=Aluminum ion, ECEC=Effective Cation Exchange Capacity. Correlation coefficient= r,p <0.05: r<0.005 not significant, r>0.007 highly significant

4. Discussion

Texturally, the soils were found to be sandy and loamy sand and the mean sand percentage value is very high. while the clay percentage is low. The result shows that the pH of the soils was generally acidic as revealed by Imadojemu *et al.* 2018. The mean value of C: N is low and this is a major factor that determines the speed of organic material decomposition as well as the nutrient release pattern which culminate to low mean value for total organic carbon (TOC). The result also shows that the top soils contents in total organic carbon were higher than the sub soils, this high TOC content of the top soil (0-15 cm) could be ascribed to deposition of leaf litter on forest floor, in addition to non-cultivation of the soil surface, which allowed accumulation of OM on soil surface. This agreed with (Hubbert *et al.*, 2001) who reported that most significant chemical changes associated with plantation forestry occurred at or near the surface of the soil and is related to the supply of organic matter.

It was observed that the labile organic carbon mean value was lower than the mean value for recalcitrant which is in accordance with these researches Bayer, *et al.*, 2006; Bayer, *et al.*,

2001; Akinbode, *et al.*, 2000; Jamala, *et al.*, 2013 and Davidson, *et al.*, 2006, these studies revealed that the proportion of recalcitrant organic carbon is greater than the labile organic carbon and it is attributed to greater stability of recalcitrant organic carbon to biological decomposition because of either their chemical structure, their adsorption to clay particles or their protection within micro aggregates. Parfitt *et al.*, (1997) also noted that variable charge mineral and soil organic matter interactions can promote a great soil organic matter protection against biological decomposition.

The concentration of labile soil organic carbon was observed to have low mean value in the land use management systems, this could be the results of increased rate of humification in these soils. Bayer, *et al.*, (2006) reported that the content of labile soil organic carbon was lower than the recalcitrant soil organic carbon in the most Brazilian soils. According to Adejuyigbe, *et al.*, (2000), the labile soil organic carbon is a more labile fraction of the soil organic carbon which is the most readily formed and when it decomposes, it serves as an important substrate for mineralization process in the soil. The level of this fraction therefore, could be an essential determinant of the

fertility status of savanna soils. Bescansa, *et al.*, (2006) stated that, labile organic carbon is differences.

Figure 2a. Map showing the geospatial distribution of Labile Organic Carbon contents for depth 0-15 cm of the location.

Figure 2b. Map showing the geospatial distribution of Labile Organic Carbon contents for depth 15-30 cm of the location, cont'd.

Figure 3a. Map showing the geospatial distribution of Recalcitrant Organic Carbon contents for depth 0-15 cm of the location.

Figure 3b. Map showing the geospatial distribution of Recalcitrant Organic Carbon contents for depth 15-30 cm of the location.

Figure 2a shows the pattern of geospatial LOC at depth 0-15 cm are Iviari, Aviodor and distribution of LOC for soils of the location for Ekwosto. Figure 2b shows communities with depth 0-15 cm, the community with high high percentage content of LOC for depth 15-30 cm, they are Yara, Itogbo and Ithavugbe communities with low percentage content of while the communities with low percentage

LOC at depth 15-30 cm are Agor, Agenebode, Emekweme Bode, Ofugbo, Ekwosto, Aigiere, Aviodor and Iviari. Figure a show high percentage content of ROC for depth 0-15 cm to be Yara, Iyukwe and Iyanipodi while the communities with low percentage ROC at depth 0-15 cm are Iviari, Aviodor, Aigiere, Ofugbo and Emekweme Bode. Figure 3b shows that Agenebode has the highest percentage content of ROC at depth 15-30 cm while Emekweme Bode, Ofugbo, Ekwosto, Aigiere, Aviodor and Iviari, Yara, Iyukwe, Iyanipodi and Itogbo have low percentage content at depth 15-30 cm.

The soils were generally acidic and sandy loamy in texture and the horizontal distributions of organic carbon were generally higher than the vertical and this could be ascribed to deposition of leaf litter on forest floor, non-cultivation of the soil surface, which allowed accumulation of organic matter on soil surface. The geospatial distribution maps of labile organic carbon and recalcitrant organic carbon contents of the soils across the location were off different pattern.

The appropriate soil management best practices recommended are conservation of tillage, cover crops, intensive crop rotation with pasture, organic amendment (i.e. animal manure) and minimal grazing.

5. Conclusion

The study shows that total Organic carbon fractions (labile and recalcitrant fraction) and its distribution in the soils varied according to locations, topsoil depth and the land use pattern. In both cultivated and uncultivated soils, TOC pool decreased with topsoil depth, uncultivated soils stored higher TOC than the cultivated soils at 0–15 cm, and 15–30 cm depth. The study also revealed that areas that

has cashew plantation has low LOC while secondary forest area has high LOC. This present study has contributed to generating a baseline data regarding the different forms and distribution of organic carbon in soils in the derived savannah (Etsako East and Local Government Area) area in Edo State, South-South, Nigeria.

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